

DYNAMICS OF THE SPREAD OF ALLERGIC DISEASES IN BUKHARA REGION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15239673>

Abstract. An analysis of the dynamics of allergic diseases in the Bukhara region over the past five years was conducted. The age was taken into account, according to which the studies were conducted and the corresponding conclusions were made. Depending on the allergic disease, factors were established that could contribute to its spread depending on a particular category of the population.

Keywords: allergic diseases, allergy, dermatitis, asthma, rhinitis.

INTRODUCTION

Health is the main value of a person. It is the state of health that determines how long and how fully a person will live. According to forecasts of the World Health Organization, the 21st century will become the era of allergies, because the prevalence of allergic diseases began to increase 2-3 times every 10 years and reached epidemic proportions. Currently, allergic pathology is among the six most common human diseases. According to statistics, every fifth inhabitant of our planet suffers from allergies: every sixth American, every fourth German, from 15 to 35% of Russians. The reasons for this phenomenon are associated with a number of factors contributing to the allergization of the population: deterioration of the environmental situation; increased contact of the population with chemicals - both in production and at home; unhealthy diet, use of products with preservatives, dyes, food additives, an increase in the number of people with pathology of the digestive system; growing urbanization, lifestyle changes, an increase in the number of stressful situations, an increase in the number of people with antisocial behavior; changes in the structure of morbidity and sickness of the population, more frequent flu epidemics; increased production and consumption of drugs and self-medication. Analysis of the role of the listed factors proves their influence on the prevalence of allergic diseases and does not allow us to hope for a decrease in morbidity in the coming years [1, 2].

MAIN PART

Allergic diseases (bronchial asthma, hay fever, urticaria, allergic rhinitis, dermatitis, drug and food allergies) are widespread throughout the world. Today, according to the World Health Organization (WHO), every sixth inhabitant of the Earth is predisposed to or suffers from some form of allergy, and the number of patients is growing rapidly. In some countries, more than 15% of the population suffers from various allergic diseases, the most common being bronchial asthma, hay fever, allergic rhinitis, and urticaria. The main reason for this is considered to be the widespread use of synthetic drugs, primarily antibiotics. One of the main factors in the spread of allergic diseases is the rapid development of the chemical industry and the associated emergence of a large number of various synthetic materials, dyes, washing powders and other various industrial and household substances, many of which can be allergens [3]. The degree of pollution of the environment (air and soil) - the ecological situation in the region of residence - is of no small importance in the growth of allergic diseases.

The following research methods were used to solve the tasks:

1. Theoretical analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological literature.

2. Analytical methods.
3. Methods of mathematical statistics [4].

The analysis of scientific and methodological literature made it possible to determine the theoretical prerequisites and objectives of the study, as well as to establish the degree of elaboration of the issue under study.

All results of experimental studies were processed using the methods of mathematical statistics described in the relevant manuals. Calculations were performed using the integrated system for complex statistical analysis and data processing Statistic 5.7 for Windows. The study was organized in three stages, taking into account the specifics of each of the tasks solved in the work. At the first stage, theoretical analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological literature devoted to this problem were carried out. At the second stage, statistical analysis of allergic diseases in the Bukhara region was carried out. At the third stage, mathematical processing of the collected material was carried out; the main results of the study were identified, conclusions were formulated and the work was designed.

CONCLUSION

As a result of our research, the following was revealed:

1. The incidence of allergies among different age groups of the population of the Bukhara region in 2020 to 2024. The following trends are revealed:

- the morbidity and incidence of allergic rhinitis decreases among children, adolescents and adults;
- the morbidity and incidence of bronchial asthma in children increases by 1.5 times, among adolescents by 2.5 times, among adults by 10 times;
- the morbidity and incidence of allergic atopic dermatitis increases among children by 2 times, adolescents by 4.5 times, adults by 2.5 times;
- the morbidity and incidence of contact allergic dermatitis decreases among children, increases among adolescents and adults.

2. The most common allergic diseases are: among children and adolescents - atopic and contact dermatitis, and among the adult population - contact dermatitis and bronchial asthma.

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